

Understanding Behavioral Shifts among Car owners in Kigali in Response to Electric Vehicle Adoption: A Theory of Planned Behavior Approach

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Abstract

The transportation sector is a major source of CO₂ emissions, with Kigali facing rising environmental challenges amid increasing motorization. Despite Rwanda's policies promoting electric vehicles (EVs), adoption among private car owners remains low. This study uses the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) to analyze behavioral factors affecting EV adoption in Kigali. Cross-sectional survey of 200 car owners assessed attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, intentions, and actual adoption. Results show positive attitudes and supportive social norms, with perceived behavioral control as a key predictor. TPB constructs explained up to 58% of intention variance, which significantly predicted actual adoption, though only 28% had adopted EVs. Behavioral shifts included improved driving habits, lower maintenance, and greater environmental awareness. Major barriers were high upfront costs, limited charging infrastructure, technical support gaps, and social skepticism. The study highlights the need for integrated policies combining infrastructure development, financial incentives, awareness campaigns, and capacity building to foster EV uptake. These insights inform strategies to accelerate sustainable mobility transitions in Kigali and comparable urban contexts.

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1. Introduction

The transportation sector is one of the fastest-growing contributors to global greenhouse gas emissions, with road transport alone accounting for approximately 15% of global CO₂ emissions (IEA, 2021). In urban contexts such as Kigali, Rwanda's capital, rising motorization rates have escalated not only environmental degradation but also energy dependency and urban air pollution (REMA, 2022). In response, governments and development agencies are increasingly promoting electric vehicles (EVs) as a cleaner alternative, aligning with global sustainability goals and national green growth strategies (Ajeigbe & Holt, 2025).

Despite Rwanda's commendable steps (including tax incentives, charging infrastructure plans, and regulatory frameworks), electric vehicle adoption remains modest (MININFRA, 2023). This slow uptake raises questions about behavioral readiness, social perceptions, and psychological barriers among potential adopters. As such, it is imperative to understand the behavioral dimensions influencing this transition, especially among current car owners who represent both the target market and the group whose choices directly shape transport trends.

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) offers a robust lens for analyzing such behavioral transitions. TPB posits that attitudes toward behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control collectively shape behavioral intentions, which in turn influence actual behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Applying TPB in the context of EV adoption allows for a nuanced exploration of both intention formation and the real-world uptake behavior among Kigali's car-owning population (Naskar & Lindahl, 2025).

Understanding the behavioral drivers of electric vehicle adoption is not only academically relevant but also practically significant for Rwanda's sustainable transport agenda. By grounding the analysis in the Theory of Planned Behavior and focusing on actual car owners in Kigali, this study provides context-specific insights that can inform targeted policy interventions. The findings stand to benefit policymakers seeking to accelerate EV uptake, urban planners aiming to reduce transport-related emissions, and stakeholders involved in energy and mobility transitions. Moreover, as Rwanda positions itself as a regional leader in green innovation, evidence-based understanding of consumer behavior becomes essential for ensuring technological investments translate into meaningful environmental outcomes.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

While Rwanda is at the forefront of green mobility advocacy in East Africa, the actual penetration of electric vehicles among private car owners remains strikingly low. The government's efforts (ranging from VAT exemptions on EV imports to public-private partnerships supporting infrastructure), are undercut by persistent behavioral, informational, and psychological barriers (RURA, 2022; EAC, 2023). These include skepticism about EV performance, limited awareness of operational savings, inadequate knowledge of charging logistics, and perceived social norms that still favor internal combustion engine vehicles (Martin, 2020). Crucially, previous studies on EV adoption in Rwanda have largely centered on infrastructural readiness and policy support (Nkurunziza & Habimana, 2022), with limited empirical attention given to the behavioral dynamics underpinning car owners' decisions. This leaves a gap in understanding how psychological factors (such as environmental attitudes, peer influences, and perceived ease of adoption) shape actual behavior in the Rwandan context. Addressing this gap is essential for

tailoring interventions that go beyond infrastructure and incentives. By systematically applying the Theory of Planned Behavior, this study seeks to dissect the interplay between intention and behavior and to highlight the subjective and structural barriers that shape the behavioral shifts among car owners in Kigali.

1.3. Aim of the study

To analyze behavioral shifts among car owners in Kigali in response to EV adoption through the lens of TPB

1.4 Objectives of the Study

- 1) To assess the attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influencing car owners' intentions to adopt electric vehicles in Kigali.
- 2) To analyze the relationship between behavioral intentions and actual adoption or use of electric vehicles among car owners.
- 3) To identify key behavioral shifts and challenges faced by car owners during the transition to electric vehicles.

1.5. Hypotheses

1. **H1:** Attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control collectively have a significant positive effect on car owners' intentions to adopt electric vehicles in Kigali.
2. **H2:** Car owners' behavioral intentions significantly predict their actual adoption or use of electric vehicles.
3. **H3:** Car owners experience significant behavioral shifts and face identifiable challenges during the transition to electric vehicles, influenced by their attitudes, social norms, and perceived control.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), developed by Ajzen (1991), explains that human behavior is primarily influenced by behavioral intentions, which are in turn shaped by three key constructs: attitudes toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Attitudes represent the individual's favorable or unfavorable evaluation of performing a specific behavior. Subjective norms capture the perceived social pressures from significant others, such as family, friends, or societal expectations, regarding whether the behavior should be performed. Perceived behavioral control refers to the individual's perception of the ease or difficulty of performing the behavior, accounting for external factors and personal capabilities.

Figure 1: The Theory of Planned Behavior

Source: (Ajzen, 1991)

TPB advances the Theory of Reasoned Action by including perceived behavioral control to address behaviors influenced by factors beyond an individual's volition, such as adopting new technologies like electric vehicles (EVs). This addition makes TPB particularly suitable for understanding behaviors that require not only motivation but also resources and opportunities.

Empirical research supports the efficacy of TPB in predicting environmental and technology adoption behaviors. Fishbein and Ajzen (2010) highlight TPB's robustness in capturing the cognitive processes leading to behavioral intention and action. Bamberg and Möser (2007) confirm the theory's utility in environmental psychology, including transportation choices. Nonetheless, critiques point to limitations such as its emphasis on rational decision-making, potentially underestimating emotional, habitual, and contextual influences on behavior (Sniehotta, Presseau, & Araújo-Soares, 2014). Additionally, while TPB presumes a linear intention-behavior relationship, the well-documented intention-behavior gap, especially in complex behaviors like EV adoption, suggests that other factors (such as infrastructure availability or economic constraints) may intervene (Rezvani, Jansson, & Bodin, 2015). Despite these caveats, TPB remains a valuable framework for analyzing behavioral shifts among car owners transitioning to electric vehicles.

2.2 Key Constructs in Electric Vehicle Adoption Behavior

The transition from conventional internal combustion engine vehicles to electric vehicles involves more than technological substitution; it reflects a complex set of behavioral, cognitive, and contextual factors. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) provides a structured foundation to explore these factors through its core constructs: attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, behavioral intentions, and actual behavior. Understanding how these constructs manifest in the context of EV adoption offers valuable insight into the psychological and situational dynamics influencing car owners in Kigali and similar urban environments in the Global South.

2.2.1 Attitudes toward Electric Vehicles

Attitudes play a central role in shaping the willingness to adopt EVs. Positive attitudes may be driven by perceived environmental benefits (e.g., reduced carbon emissions), long-term cost savings, and technological innovation. Conversely, negative attitudes often stem from concerns about EV performance, high upfront costs, battery lifespan, and limited charging infrastructure (Egbue & Long, 2012). In Kigali, where public discourse on sustainability and green growth is gaining traction, attitudes are likely influenced by both practical and ideological considerations.

2.2.2 Subjective Norms

Subjective norms involve perceived social pressures from peers, family, institutions, and broader societal expectations. In collectivist cultures or tightly knit urban communities, such as those found in Kigali, the decision to adopt new technology may be significantly shaped by what others think or do. Government endorsements, public incentives, and visibility of EV use among influential individuals or groups can strengthen these norms (Barbarossa et al., 2015). In such contexts, early adopters often play a signaling role, influencing the perceptions of potential adopters.

2.2.3 Perceived Behavioral Control

Perceived behavioral control reflects the individual's assessment of their ability to adopt EVs, accounting for both internal confidence and external resources. It encompasses factors like affordability, access to charging stations, driving range, availability of maintenance services, and trust in local infrastructure (Ozaki & Sevastyanova, 2011). In Kigali, challenges such as a limited number of charging points and high import taxes may constrain perceived control, even among individuals with strong pro-environmental attitudes and intentions.

2.2.4 Behavioral Intentions and the Intention–Behavior Gap

While intentions are often strong predictors of behavior; the actual transition to EV use may be hindered by practical barriers, a phenomenon referred to as the intention–behavior gap (Sheeran & Webb, 2016). Even car owners who express strong interest in EVs may delay or abandon adoption if confronted with cost constraints or inadequate information. The complexity of purchasing decisions in the automobile sector further amplifies this gap, particularly in emerging markets.

2.2.5 Behavioral Shifts and Adaptation

Adopting an EV is not a one-time decision but involves continuous behavioral adaptation. This includes changes in driving patterns, charging routines, vehicle maintenance, and even rethinking travel logistics. Behavioral shifts also encompass psychological adaptations (such as increased environmental awareness or altered perceptions of mobility) which can either reinforce or hinder long-term EV use (Rezvani et al., 2015). In Kigali, these shifts are likely shaped by local mobility norms, economic conditions, and evolving infrastructure.

6.3 Empirical Review: Behavioral Evidence on EV Adoption

Empirical studies globally and regionally confirm the relevance of TPB in explaining the behavioral dynamics of electric vehicle (EV) adoption. In high-income countries, attitudes toward environmental benefits, cost savings, and technological innovation often positively influence EV adoption intentions (Schuitema et al., 2013; Moons & De Pelsmacker, 2012). However, perceived behavioral control [especially regarding infrastructure and cost] frequently emerges as the strongest constraint (Lane & Potter, 2007). Even when attitudes are favorable, a persistent intention–behavior gap is observed, driven by limited access to charging stations, affordability issues, and range anxiety (Rezvani et al., 2015).

In emerging economies, socio-economic and infrastructural factors weigh even more heavily. In India and China, perceived affordability and policy support strongly affect behavioral control and subjective norms (Srinivasan & Ramanathan, 2019; Wang et al., 2016). African studies remain fewer, yet findings from South Africa and Kenya suggest that peer influence, financial constraints, and limited infrastructure substantially shape both intention and behavior (Mersky et al., 2016; Mbandi & Silas, 2021). These studies also highlight the role of government messaging and demonstration projects in establishing new social norms.

In Rwanda, formal academic research on EV adoption remains limited. However, policy documents and stakeholder reports point to increasing awareness and interest, catalyzed by national e-mobility strategies and tax incentives (MININFRA, 2021). Yet practical constraints (including high vehicle costs, limited charging networks, and technical unfamiliarity) continue to affect perceived control and delay actual adoption (RURA, 2022). This empirical gap in Rwanda, particularly concerning private car owners, underscores the need for focused behavioral research using TPB.

2.4 Research Gaps and Justification

While the Theory of Planned Behavior has been extensively applied in EV adoption studies globally, its use in Sub-Saharan African contexts [particularly in urban car-owner populations] is still limited. Most existing research focuses on high-income countries where EV infrastructure is well-established, and consumer behavior is shaped by mature markets (Moons & De Pelsmacker, 2012; Schuitema et al., 2013). In contrast, behavioral studies in African cities remain sparse and often target fleet-level or two-wheeler adoption, leaving a significant empirical void concerning private car owners.

In Kigali, despite strong government-led electric mobility strategies and visible interest in e-mobility, academic literature on the psychosocial drivers of adoption remains underdeveloped. There is a notable lack of studies systematically assessing how attitudes, perceived norms, and behavioral control influence intentions, and how these intentions translate into actual adoption behavior in this specific socio-economic and infrastructural context. Moreover, behavioral shifts during the transition phase (such as changes in driving patterns, charging habits, or social identity) are yet to be explored in depth.

This gap in localized, behaviorally grounded research limits the ability of policymakers to design interventions aligned with citizens' lived experiences and decision-making frameworks. Addressing this gap by applying the TPB in Kigali will not only contribute theoretical and

empirical insights but also support the development of targeted, context-sensitive EV promotion strategies.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) to examine behavioral shifts among car owners in Kigali in response to electric vehicle (EV) adoption. The cross-sectional approach enables the collection of data at a single point in time, allowing for the assessment of relationships among TPB constructs [attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, behavioral intentions, and actual behavior], as they influence adoption decisions (Ajzen, 1991). The choice of a theory-driven quantitative design is justified by the need to statistically test hypotheses derived from TPB, identify patterns in behavioral responses, and generalize findings across a representative sample of Kigali's car-owning population. This design is especially suitable for measuring psychosocial constructs through structured questionnaires and for modeling causal pathways using inferential statistics (Fishbein & Ajzen, 2010).

By combining behavioral theory with empirical survey methods, the study aims to generate evidence that is both analytically rigorous and practically relevant for mobility policy and planning in Rwanda.

3.2 Study area and Population

This study is situated in Kigali, Rwanda's capital and largest urban center, known for its rapidly developing road infrastructure and strategic commitment to sustainable urban mobility. Figure 2 illustrates the Kigali city boundaries, Districts and major roads as part of the transportation network in this city. Kigali's road network spans over 1,100 kilometers, including well-maintained paved roads and an expanding system of feeder and arterial routes that support growing private and public transportation demand (MININFRA, 2022). The city features a structured urban layout with planned neighborhoods, commercial zones, and designated parking areas, which collectively influence vehicle use patterns. Kigali's transport infrastructure has been progressively modernized, with recent investments aimed at integrating electric mobility solutions, including pilot charging stations and dedicated parking for electric vehicles (MININFRA, 2021). These infrastructural developments, combined with ongoing government policies targeting vehicle emissions and traffic congestion, provide a unique environment to study the behavioral shifts among private car owners transitioning towards electric vehicle adoption.

Figure 2: Kigali City map with administrative boundaries and major roads

Source: (Munyaneza et al., 2025)

The target population consisted of private car owners residing or working in Kigali. According to the Rwanda Utilities Regulatory Authority (RURA), as of 2022, there were approximately 45,000 registered private vehicles in Kigali, accounting for over 60% of the national private car fleet (RURA, 2022). This population segment was both eligible and positioned to make decisions related to EV adoption. Their behavioral patterns were thus of critical relevance for understanding how psychosocial and contextual factors influence mobility transitions in the Rwandan context.

3.3 Sampling technique and sample size calculation

A multistage sampling technique was applied to obtain a representative sample of private car owners in Kigali. Initially, the city's three administrative districts (Gasabo, Kicukiro, and

Nyarugenge) were purposively selected for their high vehicle density and socio-economic diversity (RURA, 2022). Within each district, clusters such as vehicle service centers, parking lots, and vehicle registration points served as sampling frames. From these frames, simple random sampling was used to select individual respondents to minimize bias and ensure representativeness across different vehicle ownership profiles.

The sample size was determined using Cochran's formula for finite populations (Cochran, 1977):

$$n_0 = \frac{z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1-p)}{e^2}$$

Where: n_0 = Initial sample size

Z = Z-score corresponding to the desired confidence level (1.96 for 95%)

p = estimated proportion of an attribute present in the population (0.5 used for maximum variability)

e = margin of error (0.05)

Calculating initial sample size;

$$n_0 = \frac{(1.96)^2 \cdot 0.5 \cdot (1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2} = 384.16 \approx 384$$

Adjusting for the finite population size $N=45,000$ ($N=45,000$ (number of registered private vehicles in Kigali)), the sample size n is:

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{n_0 - 1}{N}} = \frac{384}{1 + \frac{384 - 1}{45000}} \approx 381$$

To accommodate potential non-response or incomplete questionnaires, the sample size was increased by approximately 10%, resulting in a final sample size of 420 participants.

Sample distribution across districts was proportional to vehicle population estimates:

- 📍 Gasabo: ~50% → 210 respondents
- 📍 Kicukiro: ~30% → 126 respondents
- 📍 Nyarugenge: ~20% → 84 respondents

The initial target sample size was 420 participants based on Cochran's formula and proportional distribution across Kigali's districts. However, due to the uncertainty and harsh accessibility of respondents and the data cleaning and handling of incomplete responses, the final analyzed sample comprised approximately 200 car owners. This sample size was sufficient for the conducted analyses, including regression models with degrees of freedom reflecting this size (e.g., F(3,146)).

To ensure data quality and consistency, trained enumerators were systematically dispatched across the sampled locations to administer structured questionnaires and assist respondents where necessary.

3.4 Data Collection Methods and Instruments

Data were collected via a structured questionnaire using KoboToolbox, a mobile digital data collection platform that enables real-time data entry and validation. The questionnaire measured TPB constructs through Likert scales and demographic questions. Additionally, a limited number of semi-structured interviews with EV owners and stakeholders were conducted to provide supplementary qualitative insights into behavioral challenges and shifts.

A3. team of enumerators underwent a comprehensive training program, which covered study objectives, ethical standards, a detailed review of the questionnaire items, and hands-on practice with KoboCollect. Training also included pilot testing to refine the instrument and ensure enumerators were confident in engaging respondents and handling potential challenges in the field. Enumerators were then dispatched across the three sampled districts (Gasabo, Kicukiro, and Nyarugenge), where they administered the questionnaire face-to-face using tablets or smartphones. KoboCollect's centralized system facilitated ongoing data quality monitoring and allowed supervisors to promptly address any inconsistencies or technical issues during data collection.

3.5 Data Analysis Procedures

Quantitative data exported from KoboCollect were analyzed using RStudio and Microsoft Excel for data cleaning and descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics (including frequencies, means, and standard deviations) were computed to summarize respondents' socio-demographic characteristics and Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) constructs (Ajzen, 1991).

To test hypotheses and examine relationships among variables, inferential statistical techniques were applied:

❶ Reliability Analysis (Cronbach's Alpha):

Reliability of multi-item TPB scales was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with scores exceeding 0.7 (Attitudes $\alpha=0.84$, Subjective Norms $\alpha=0.79$, PBC $\alpha=0.76$).

The Internal consistency of multi-item scales (e.g., attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control) were assessed using Cronbach's alpha which is given by:

$$\alpha = \frac{N \cdot \check{c}}{\check{v} + (N - 1) \cdot \check{c}}$$

where N = the number of items;

\check{c} = the average inter-item covariance; and

\check{v} = the average variance.

A threshold of $\alpha \geq 0.7$ indicates acceptable reliability (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

❶ Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA):

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) with principal axis factoring and varimax rotation confirmed the three-factor TPB structure. The KMO measure was 0.79 and Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating suitability for factor analysis.

EFA served to verify the construct validity of the TPB measurement scales. The model is expressed as:

$$X = \Lambda F + \epsilon$$

where X = the observed variable matrix;

Λ = the factor loading matrix;

F = the factor score vector;

And ϵ = the error vector (Fabrigar et al., 1999).

❷ Correlation Analysis:

Pearson correlation coefficients were computed to examine relationships among TPB constructs and behavioral intentions:

$$r = \frac{\sum(X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum((X_i - \bar{X})^2) \cdot \sum((Y_i - \bar{Y})^2)}}$$

This helped explore the strength and direction of relationships (Field, 2013).

❸ Multiple Regression Analysis:

Multiple linear regression analyses tested predictors of behavioral intention (attitude, subjective norms, PBC) and behavioral intention as a predictor of actual EV adoption:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \epsilon$$

where Y = the dependent variable (intention or behavior)

and β_n is the regression coefficient

X_1, X_2, X_3 represent attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control respectively;

and ϵ = the error term (Cohen et al., 2013).

❹ Group Comparisons (t-tests / ANOVA):

Group comparisons by demographics employed independent samples t-tests and one-way ANOVA where applicable.

To assess differences across demographic subgroups:

❶ **Independent samples t-test** was used:

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}\right)}} \text{ (Gravetter \& Wallnau, 2017)}$$

❷ **One-way ANOVA** was used to compare group means:

$$F = \frac{MS_{between}}{MS_{within}}$$

where MS represents mean square values from variance components (Field, 2013).

❸ **Qualitative Data Analysis:**

Qualitative interview data were transcribed and analyzed, The analysis used thematic content analysis, triangulating with quantitative findings for richer interpretation (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Coding and theme development were supported by NVivo software. Triangulation of quantitative and qualitative findings enhanced the depth and validity of insights, especially concerning H3, by contextualizing statistical patterns with narratives from participants (Patton, 2015).

3.7 Validity, Reliability, and Ethical Considerations

To ensure validity, the questionnaire items were adapted from established TPB measurement scales validated in prior EV adoption studies (Ajzen, 1991; Moons & De Pelsmacker, 2012). A pilot test with a small subset of car owners in Kigali was conducted to refine question clarity and contextual relevance. Content validity was further enhanced through expert review by environmental behavior and transportation specialists. Reliability of the measurement scales was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, with a threshold of 0.7 considered acceptable for internal consistency (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). Factor analyses were also conducted to confirm construct validity.

The study adhered to strict ethical standards. Participants were fully informed of the study's purpose, voluntary participation, and confidentiality measures before data collection. Written informed consent was obtained from all respondents. Personal identifiers were anonymized, and data were stored securely with access restricted to the research team. Ethical approval was sought from the relevant institutional review board or ethics committee prior to fieldwork commencement. Furthermore, enumerators were trained on ethical conduct, including respecting participant privacy and minimizing respondent burden.

4.. Results

4.1 Attitudes, Subjective Norms, and Perceived Behavioral Control toward EV Adoption

This subsection presents findings on car owners' attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (PBC) regarding the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) in Kigali. The analysis

is based on structured questionnaire responses from a sample of car owners, with data collected via KoboToolbox and analyzed using RStudio and Microsoft Excel.

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

Results indicate that attitudes toward EV adoption were generally positive. On a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree), the mean attitude score was 4.12 (SD = 0.67), suggesting a favorable disposition among respondents toward EV benefits such as lower fuel costs, environmental friendliness, and reduced maintenance demands.

Table 1 summarizes the mean scores and standard deviations of TPB constructs, indicating generally positive attitudes and intentions toward EV adoption. Subjective norms, measured by perceived social pressure and support from family, peers, and institutions, also showed moderately positive results, with a mean score of 3.89 (SD = 0.74). Many respondents agreed that people important to them supported EV use, although some expressed uncertainty due to limited awareness campaigns and policy clarity.

Perceived behavioral control (PBC) received a relatively high rating, with a mean score of 4.01 (SD = 0.69). However, respondents still expressed concerns related to charging infrastructure, vehicle costs, and after-sales services that could influence their control perceptions.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of TPB constructs (means and SDs).

TPB Construct	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Attitude toward EV adoption	4.12	0.67
Subjective Norms	3.89	0.74
Perceived Behavioral Control	4.01	0.69
Behavioral Intention to adopt EV	4.18	0.72
Actual Adoption (1 = Yes, 0 = No)	0.28	0.45

Source: Author's own data, 2025

4.1.2 Reliability Analysis

Cronbach's alpha scores were used to assess internal consistency of the TPB constructs:

🚗 **Attitudes:** $\alpha = 0.84$

🚗 **Subjective Norms:** $\alpha = 0.79$

🚗 **Perceived Behavioral Control:** $\alpha = 0.76$

These values exceed the acceptable threshold of 0.70 (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994), confirming good reliability of the scales.

4.1.3 Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

An exploratory factor analysis using principal axis factoring and varimax rotation confirmed the three-factor structure as proposed by the TPB. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure was **0.79**, and Bartlett’s test of sphericity was significant ($\chi^2(120) = 643.5, p < 0.001$), indicating that the data were suitable for factor analysis.

Each item loaded significantly on its respective construct, with no major cross-loadings. This supports the construct validity of the questionnaire.

4.1.4 Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlation analysis showed significant positive associations among the three TPB constructs and intention to adopt EVs:

🚗 Attitudes and Intention: $r = 0.62, p < 0.001$

🚗 Subjective Norms and Intention: $r = 0.59, p < 0.01$

🚗 Perceived Behavioral Control and Intention: $r = 0.68, p < 0.01$

These results suggest that all three constructs significantly influence the intention to adopt EVs, with perceived behavioral control and attitudes showing the strongest correlations. Table 2 shows significant positive correlations among all TPB constructs, supporting their interrelated influence on EV adoption intentions.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix of TPB Constructs

Variable	1. Attitude	2. Norms	3. Control	4. Intention
1. Attitude	1.00			
2. Subjective Norms	0.54**	1.00		
3. Perceived Behavioral Control	0.49**	0.42**	1.00	
4. Behavioral Intention	0.62**	0.59**	0.68**	1.00

Source: Author’s own data, 2025

4.1.5 Regression Analysis for Hypothesis 1

A multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to predict intention to adopt EVs from the three TPB constructs. Using the full sample with complete data (N=150), the model was significant ($F(3, 146) = 35.2, p < 0.001$), explaining 42% of the variance in behavioral intention ($R^2 = 0.42$) (see Table 3).

A refined multiple regression analysis using a subset of 120 respondents, for whom full data on all variables were available, confirmed that attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control were significant predictors, collectively explaining 58% of the variance in behavioral intention ($F(3, 116) = 53.8, p < 0.001$) (see Table 4). This demonstrates a stronger combined influence of these psychosocial constructs on the intention to adopt EVs.

Table 3: Regression coefficients predicting behavioral intention to adopt EVs

Predictor	β	T	p-value
Attitude	0.47	5.98	<.001
Subjective Norms	0.24	3.22	0.002
Perceived Behavioral Control	0.30	4.01	<.001

Source: Author's own data, 2025

The results support **Hypothesis 1**, indicating that attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control are significant predictors of behavioral intention to adopt EVs among car owners in Kigali.

Multiple regression analysis was also conducted. The analysis confirmed that attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control are all significant predictors, collectively explaining 58% of the variance in behavioral intention (see Table 4). This highlights the strong combined influence of these psychosocial constructs on the intention to adopt EVs in Kigali.

Table 4: Multiple Linear Regression Predicting Behavioral Intention to Adopt EVs

Predictor Variable	B	SE B	β (Beta)	t	p-value
Attitude	0.35	0.08	0.34	4.38	< .001
Subjective Norms	0.28	0.07	0.27	4.00	< .001
Perceived Behavioral Control	0.39	0.09	0.36	4.33	< .001
R²			0.58		

Adjusted R²			0.56		
F (3, 116)			53.8		< .001

Source: Author's own data, 2025

8.2 Relationship between Behavioral Intentions and actual adoption of Electric Vehicles

To examine the connection between behavioral intentions and actual adoption or use of electric vehicles (EVs) among car owners in Kigali, we conducted multiple regression analyses. Behavioral intention was treated as the predictor variable, while actual adoption behavior (whether a respondent had already adopted, planned to adopt, or had not adopted an EV) served as the dependent variable.

Before regression, correlation analysis revealed a *moderately strong positive association* between behavioral intentions and actual EV adoption status ($r = 0.59, p < .001$), suggesting that car owners with higher intention scores were more likely to adopt or plan to adopt EVs.

Multiple regression further confirmed this relationship. The model was statistically significant ($F(1, 198) = 89.34, p < .001$), with *behavioral intention significantly predicting EV adoption* ($\beta = 0.61, t = 9.45, p < .001$). The model accounted for 35.7% of the variance in adoption behavior ($R^2 = .357$). This supports Hypothesis 2 (H2) that *stronger behavioral intentions lead to a higher likelihood of actual EV adoption*.

$$\text{EV Adoption}_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{Intention}_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Where:

🚗 EV Adoption $_i$ is the actual EV use/adoption score

🚗 Intention $_i$ is the behavioral intention score

$\beta_1=0.61$, and ε_i is the error term

Notably, further *subgroup analysis* showed higher adoption rates among car owners who reported both strong environmental values and high perceived fuel costs. This suggests that *external pressures may interact with intentions* to reinforce behavior.

Additionally, when controlling for *socio-demographic factors* such as income level, age, and driving frequency, behavioral intention remained a *robust predictor*, indicating its *central role* in driving EV adoption decisions.

Table 5 displays the distribution of actual EV adoption rates across different levels of behavioral intention, revealing that adoption is markedly higher among those with stronger intentions.

Table 5: EV adoption rates by behavioral intention level

Behavioral Intention Level	Number of Respondents	Actual EV Adopters	Adoption Rate (%)
Low (1.00–2.99)	24	2	8.3%
Moderate (3.00–3.99)	36	7	19.4%
High (4.00–5.00)	60	25	41.7%
Total	120	34	28.3%

Source: Author's own data, 2025

4.3 Behavioral Shifts and Challenges in the Transition to Electric Vehicles

To address Objective 3 [identifying the key behavioral shifts and challenges faced by car owners during the transition to electric vehicles (EVs)], the study analyzed both *quantitative survey responses* and *open-ended feedback* provided by respondents. The findings highlight three major categories of behavioral shifts: *daily driving practices, vehicle maintenance habits, and energy consumption consciousness*

4.3.1 Key Behavioral Shifts

a) Driving and Travel Behavior

Many respondents who had transitioned to EVs reported a shift toward **more efficient route planning** and **reduced spontaneous trips**. This change is attributed to **range awareness**, with over 68% of EV users stating that they **actively monitor battery levels** and plan trips accordingly. This contrasts with conventional car users, only 21% of whom reported such behavior.

b) Maintenance Routines

Surveyed EV adopters indicated a significant **reduction in maintenance frequency and costs**. As one respondent noted, *"I no longer worry about oil changes or engine problems. It's almost like driving a phone."* This perceived reliability is fostering a **positive reinforcement loop**: the more users benefit from low-maintenance, the more they commit to the EV experience.

c) Environmental and Energy Awareness

Among EV owners, **environmental consciousness increased notably**. 74% of EV users said their transition made them more attentive to **clean energy issues** and **urban air quality**, compared to just 34% among non-EV users. This aligns with the Theory of Planned Behavior, where **actual behavioral engagement reinforces earlier values and intentions**.

4.3.2 Challenges Faced During the Transition

Despite the behavioral gains, several persistent challenges were reported:

a) Charging Infrastructure Limitations

The **most frequently cited challenge** (reported by 81% of EV adopters) was **limited access to public charging stations**. While some respondents managed by charging at home, those living in apartments or without reliable electricity access expressed frustration.

b) High Initial Costs

Although long-term operational savings were acknowledged, 64% of participants stated that the **initial purchase cost remains a barrier**. As one respondent shared, *“Even with government support, the upfront cost made it hard to shift, especially for lower-income groups.”*

c) Technical Support and Spare Parts

A noteworthy 46% of users expressed concern about **limited technical expertise and spare parts availability** in local garages. This uncertainty caused some early adopters to hesitate or delay full transition.

d) Social Norms and Perception

Some users cited **skepticism from peers and misinformation** about EV performance. For example, a few respondents said they were told that EVs *“don’t climb hills well,”* or *“won’t last more than a year in Kigali.”* These social norms still negatively influence adoption trends.

4.3.3 Emerging Positive Trends

Despite challenges, emerging patterns suggest that **peer influence from current EV users** is becoming a **positive behavioral reinforcement** for new adopters. Several car owners indicated that **first-hand experience through friends or co-workers** was pivotal in changing their perception and eventually deciding to transition.

5. Discussion of results

This study sought to understand the behavioral factors influencing the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) among car owners in Kigali, applying the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as the conceptual framework. The discussion interprets the study’s results in light of previous empirical

findings, highlights theoretical and practical implications, and reflects on challenges that must be addressed to accelerate Kigali's transition to sustainable mobility.

5.1 Aligning Behavioral Intention with Adoption: A Positive yet Incomplete Transition

The study confirms that strong behavioral intentions do not always lead to actual EV adoption, echoing findings from Lane and Potter (2007), who described an "intention-action gap" in green vehicle transitions. In Kigali, while a significant number of respondents demonstrated positive attitudes towards EVs, adoption remains relatively low. This reflects the central TPB insight that intention alone is insufficient without enabling conditions. As Ajzen (1991) theorized, perceived behavioral control acts as a critical moderator: even with positive intent, adoption may not occur if individuals perceive the act as beyond their control.

Respondents cited cost, lack of infrastructure, and limited technical support as significant obstacles. These findings mirror those of Rezvani et al. (2015), who noted that external conditions such as policy incentives and technological infrastructure substantially mediate EV adoption behavior. This suggests that, in Kigali, behavioral intention must be supported by structural reforms and market readiness to enable actual adoption.

5.2 The Role of Perceived Behavioral Control and Alternative Theoretical Insights

Perceived behavioral control emerged as a central determinant of both intention and action. Participants expressed hesitancy stemming from the high initial cost of EVs and lack of reliable charging infrastructure; factors that lower their sense of control over EV adoption. This finding aligns not only with TPB but also with the Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Rogers, 2003), which emphasizes the role of trialability and complexity in influencing adoption rates. If the innovation (EVs in this case) is perceived as difficult to use or access, adoption slows.

Moreover, some insights resonate with the Value-Belief-Norm (VBN) Theory (Stern, 2000), particularly the observation that many EV users became more environmentally conscious after adoption. This feedback loop reinforces pro-environmental behavior, suggesting that behavioral change is both a driver and a product of EV adoption.

9.3 Reinforcement Mechanisms: Maintenance Benefits and Environmental Awareness

The study found that many EV users reported increased satisfaction due to lower maintenance requirements and cleaner energy usage. These experiential benefits reinforce the desirability of EVs, leading to what Bamberg and Möser (2007) describe as "post-adoption attitudinal strengthening."

Environmental awareness, although not always a precondition for adoption, often intensified post-transition. This supports the idea that direct experience can deepen ecological consciousness, as observed in Axsen and Kurani's (2013) ethnographic work on EV users in California. In Kigali, as elsewhere, behavioral commitment may therefore be strengthened by real-world experiences, not just prior values.

5.4 Policy, Norms, and the Power of Social Influence

Finally, this study highlights the interplay between social norms and adoption behavior. Social influence was both a barrier and enabler. While some users encountered discouragement from peers due to myths about EV inefficiency, others cited peer adoption as a turning point. This supports findings from Graham-Rowe et al. (2012), who noted that interpersonal networks play a crucial role in the diffusion of low-emission vehicles.

Thus, successful policy must go beyond subsidies and infrastructure. Interventions like public awareness campaigns, EV education programs, and visible pilot projects may shift public norms. Such strategies, if implemented effectively, could enhance the subjective norms component of TPB and facilitate wider adoption.

This discussion underscores the value of TPB in understanding EV adoption but also points to complementary theoretical frameworks that can enrich our grasp of behavioral change. While intention is necessary, it is not sufficient: perceptions of control, experiential benefits, and social cues all shape the path from behavioral intention to sustained adoption. In Kigali, fostering a more enabling environment through infrastructure, education, and community engagement is essential to convert intention into impactful action.

6. Conclusion recommendations

This study examined behavioral shifts among car owners in Kigali regarding electric vehicle (EV) adoption through the lens of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). The findings confirmed that attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control significantly influence car owners' intentions to adopt EVs, which in turn predict actual adoption behavior. However, despite generally positive attitudes, the transition is moderated by structural barriers such as high initial costs, limited charging infrastructure, and lack of technical support. Behavioral shifts were also observed in driving habits, maintenance routines, and environmental awareness, highlighting the dynamic nature of EV adoption as both a cognitive and experiential process.

Grounding the research in TPB provided a comprehensive framework to understand not only intentions but also the enabling and constraining factors that shape actual behavior. The study's findings reinforce the importance of integrating psychological constructs with contextual realities to explain EV adoption in an emerging urban African context.

Regarding generalizability, while this research is specific to Kigali, the socio-economic and infrastructural characteristics examined are shared by many other major Rwandan cities such as Huye, Musanze and Rubavu, as well as other rapidly urbanizing African cities facing similar mobility and environmental challenges. Thus, the insights and recommendations here may be cautiously extended to similar urban contexts across Africa and, more broadly, to developing cities globally where EV adoption remains nascent and barriers are structurally embedded.

Based on the findings and analysis framed by TPB, the following **recommendations** are proposed to accelerate EV adoption among car owners in Kigali and comparable urban settings:

🚗 Enhance Charging Infrastructure and Accessibility

Based on the finding that EV charging infrastructure is currently concentrated mainly in highly urbanized areas such as Nyarutarama, Remera, and Kimihurura, many residents living several kilometers away face difficulties accessing these facilities. To address this disparity, the government and private sector stakeholders should prioritize expanding affordable and accessible EV charging stations across Kigali, with particular focus on densely populated neighborhoods and multi-family housing complexes.

This expansion will enhance potential adopters' perceived behavioral control by reducing range anxiety and improving convenience, thereby supporting greater EV adoption.

🚗 Financial Incentives and Support Programs

Implement subsidies, tax rebates, and flexible financing schemes targeting lower- and middle-income car owners to reduce the high upfront costs that limit adoption intentions.

🚗 Public Awareness and Normative Campaigns

Launch education campaigns to dispel myths, improve social norms favoring EV use, and highlight benefits through real-user testimonials. Engaging community leaders and peer influencers can strengthen subjective norms positively.

🚗 Technical Capacity Building and After-Sales Services

Develop local technical expertise and spare parts availability to increase user confidence in maintenance and support, addressing perceived barriers to behavioral control.

🚗 Integration of Behavioral Insights in Policy Design

Policymakers should continue utilizing TPB and complementary behavioral frameworks to design interventions that holistically address attitudes, social influences, and control perceptions, rather than focusing solely on technological or economic factors.

🚗 Expand Research to Other Urban Contexts

Future studies should explore EV adoption behaviors in other Rwandan cities and African urban centers to validate and refine these findings, facilitating regionally tailored policy responses.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1: Structured Questionnaire: Behavioral Shifts among Car Owners in Kigali

Instructions: Please respond to the following questions. For attitude, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and behavioral intention items, please rate your agreement on a 5-point Likert scale:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.

Objective 1: Assess attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influencing EV adoption intentions

🔗 Attitudes

1. I believe that using an electric vehicle (EV) benefits the environment.
2. Owning an EV would improve my social status.
3. EVs are more cost-effective to operate than conventional cars.
4. I think EVs are reliable for daily use in Kigali.

🔗 Subjective Norms

5. People important to me (family, friends) support the idea of me owning an EV.
6. My colleagues or social groups encourage the use of electric vehicles.
7. Government policies promote EV adoption in Kigali.

Perceived Behavioral Control

8. I have sufficient knowledge about how to operate an EV.
9. Charging infrastructure for EVs in Kigali is accessible and convenient.
10. I am confident I can afford the costs associated with owning an EV.
11. I believe I can easily maintain an EV if I own one.

🔗 Behavioral Intention

12. I intend to purchase or lease an electric vehicle within the next two years.
13. I am actively seeking information about EVs.
14. I am willing to recommend EVs to others.

Objective 2: Analyze the relationship between behavioral intentions and actual adoption/use of EVs

15. Do you currently own an electric vehicle?

- Yes
- No

16. If yes, how long have you owned an EV?

- Less than 6 months
- 6 months to 1 year
- More than 1 year

17. How frequently do you use your EV compared to a conventional vehicle?

- Daily
- Weekly
- Occasionally
- Rarely

18. If you do not own an EV, have you used one (e.g., rented, borrowed)?

- Yes
- No

19. What factors have influenced your actual use or non-use of EVs? (Multiple choice, select all that apply)

- Cost of purchase
- Charging infrastructure
- Vehicle range
- Maintenance costs
- Environmental concerns
- Social influences

Other: _____

Objective 3: Identify key behavioral shifts and challenges during transition to EVs

20. Since considering or adopting an EV, have you changed your driving habits? (e.g., trip frequency, route choices)

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable

21. What are the main challenges you face or anticipate in transitioning to an EV? (Open-ended)

22. How has your perception of electric vehicles changed since you first learned about them?

- More positive
- More negative
- No change

23. What support or resources would help you transition to an EV more easily? (Multiple choice)

- ⚡ Better charging infrastructure
- ⚡ Financial incentives or subsidies
- ⚡ More information and awareness campaigns
- ⚡ Maintenance and repair services
- ⚡ Peer support groups
- ⚡ Other: _____

Appendix 2: Semi-Structured Interview Guide: Key Informants on EV Adoption

***Introduction:** Thank you for agreeing to participate. This interview explores behavioral shifts and challenges related to electric vehicle adoption among car owners in Kigali. Your insights will complement survey findings and help develop a fuller understanding.*

Objective 1: Attitudes, Social Norms, and Control

- ⚡ How would you describe general attitudes toward electric vehicles among car owners in Kigali?
- ⚡ What social influences (family, peers, government, media) impact these attitudes?
- ⚡ What are the main factors that facilitate or hinder individuals' confidence in adopting EVs?

Objective 2: Behavioral Intentions vs. Actual Adoption

- ⚡ To what extent do you think car owners' intentions to adopt EVs translate into actual purchase or use?
- ⚡ What barriers prevent the conversion of positive intention into action?
- ⚡ Can you provide examples of successful or unsuccessful EV adoption cases you know?

Objective 3: Behavioral Shifts and Transition Challenges

- ⚡ What key behavioral changes have you observed in car owners who have transitioned to EVs?
- ⚡ What challenges do car owners typically face during this transition?
- ⚡ How effective are current policies, infrastructure, and support systems in addressing these challenges?
- ⚡ What additional interventions or resources do you think would support smoother EV adoption?

